

Cythara thapsiae Oberling, 1970 senior synonym of *Mangiliella fieldeni* van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978 (Gastropoda, Conoidea, Mangeliidae)

Cythara thapsiae Oberling, 1970, sinonimia anterior de *Mangiliella fieldeni* van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978 (Gastropoda, Conoidea, Mangeliidae)

Bruno AMATI*, Massimo APPOLLONI** and Marco OLIVERIO***

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ABSTRACT

A neotype is designated for *Cythara thapsiae* Oberling, 1970, based on topotypic material. Since the name cannot be dismissed as *nomen oblitum*, *Mangelia thapsiae* (Oberling, 1970) is the valid name for the species so far known as *Mangelia fieldeni* (van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978).

RESUMEN

Se designa un neotipo para *Cythara thapsiae* Oberling, 1970, basado en material topotípico. Dado que el nombre no puede ser descartado como *nomen oblitum*, *Mangelia thapsiae* (Oberling, 1970) es el nombre válido para la especie hasta ahora conocida como *Mangelia fieldeni* (Van Aartsen y Fehr-de Wal, 1978).

INTRODUCTION

Jean Jacques OBERLING (1970) introduced several new gastropod taxa from the Mediterranean, some of which have been revised and his names are considered the valid ones (OLIVERIO, AMATI & NOFRONI, 1986; AMATI, 1987; 2012; PALAZZI, 1987; MOOLENBEEK, HOENSELAAR & OLIVERIO, 1991; OLIVERIO, 1993; 1995; TRINGALI, 2001; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2014), whereas others have been synonymized or are still considered as *nomina dubia* (OBERLING, 1971; MOOLENBEEK *ET AL.*, 1991; NOFRONI & TRINGALI, 1996; AMATI & SMRIGLIO,

2016; ROMANI & SCUDERI, 2016; CLEMAM, 2017; MOLLUSCABASE, 2017).

Among the taxa with uncertain status is *Cythara thapsiae* Oberling, 1970. The genus *Cythara* Schumacher, 1817 (type species *C. striata* Schumacher, 1817 *nomen dubium*) was used for several Mediterranean mangeliids (e.g. PARENZAN, 1970; NORDSIECK, 1977) until van AARTSEN & FEHR-DE WAL (1978) showed that the genus *Mangelia* Risso, 1826 (type species *M. striolata* Risso, 1826 by subsequent designation by Gray, 1847: see SPADA & DELLA BELLA, 2010: 76), should

* Largo Giuseppe Veratti, 37-D, I-00146 Rome, Italy. bruno_amati@yahoo.it

** Museo Civico di Zoologia, Via Ulisse Aldrovandi, 18, I-00197 Rome, Italy. massimo.appolloni@comune.roma.it

*** Department of Biology and Biotechnologies "Charles Darwin", Sapienza University of Rome, Viale dell'Università 32, I-00185 Rome, Italy. marco.oliverio@uniroma1.it

be used. *Mangiliella* Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883 (type species *Pleurotoma multilineolata* Deshayes, 1835 by original designation) has been proposed to contain the series of *Mangelia*-like species with paucispiral protoconch and thus lecithotrophic development. Almost all recent specialists (including ourselves) agree with Bouchet (1990) that considered this subdivision phylogenetically artificial, and a total of 26 extant Mediterranean species are currently comprised in the single genus *Mangelia* (CLEMAM, 2017; MOLLUSCABASE, 2017).

The original description (OBERLING, 1970) of *Cythara thapsiae* and the subsequent one by the same author (OBERLING, 1971), fit quite perfectly *Mangiliella fieldieni* van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978. We report here below the two descriptions of *Cythara thapsiae* and that of *Mangiliella fieldieni*.

"*Cythara thapsiae*, spec. nov. Un petit *Cythara* de Magnisi en Sicile. La forme est celle d'un *C. vauquelini* adulte, mais avec une pente surangulaire plus raide, et l'angle plus pointu. La sculpture spirale est absente en dessus de l'angle et en dessous consiste en sillons assez grossier au nombre de 6 sur l'avant dernier tour. A peu près 12 côtes transverses par tour. Couleur brunâtre avec tache foncée en dehors du labre et parfois une bande subsuturale sombre. Cette espèce ressemble fortement au jeune de *C. sicula* Rve., mais a une base plus large: les présents spécimens sont d'ailleurs tous adultes." (OBERLING, 1970: 4).

"*Cythara thapsiae* Oberl. Un petit (5 tours, 5.5 x 2.5 mm.) *Cythara*, au galbe semblable à celui de *C. vauquelini* Payr.. Tours fortement angulés à la partie supérieure, côté du tour au-dessus de l'angle incliné de 45° à 60°, cordons spiraux présents au-dessous de l'angle, aplatis, de largeur inégale, avec espaces très exigus. Environ 8 cordons sur l'avant-dernier tour, plus de 30 sur le dernier. Cordons obsolescents ou absents au-dessus de l'angle. Protoconque élevée, plutôt comme chez le sous-genre *Mangiliella*. Couleur variant du blanc au brun foncé, avec bande subsuturale sombre à 3/5 de distance du sommet du dernier tour, cette bande se manifestant

sur le bourrelet par une tache brune. Bourrelet assez médiocre, sinus peu profond. *Cythara thapsiae*, dont la localité type est Magnisi, en Sicile, ressemble au *C. vauquelini* Payr. Mais est plus petit, plus étroit, avec tours ornés de cordons bien développés, etc..." (OBERLING, 1971: 6).

"*Mangiliella fieldieni* (Monterosato MS) nov. spec. (Fig. 4). Shell: slender fusiform, rather thin, semitransparent.

Whorls: the 4-5 adult whorls are keeled in such a way that the lower two thirds are more or less cylindrical and the upper third shelves down in a straight line from the suture to the keel, which corresponds with the first spiral band; the apex consists of about one and a half whorls which are completely smooth and «peg-like».

Sculpture: narrow axial ribs, nearly straight and inclined to the right, numbering 9-14 on the body whorl; these ribs extend to the base of the shell as well as to the suture; on the adapical part of the whorls where the sinus is situated the axial ribs are narrower and somewhat curved; in each whorl the lower two thirds carries from four to six spiral bands which pass over the ribs; these spiral bands are separated by relatively narrow interstices; on the body whorl there are about ten more of these spiral bands, the last three of which wind closely around the pillar.

Colour: buff; some of the spirals being whitish; some specimens are nearly completely white, tinged with brown along the upper suture only,

Suture: clearly ranked, but not very deep, undulated by the axial ribs.

Mouth: somewhat expanded, occupying somewhat more than half the total length.

Outer lip: strengthened by a rather well developed labial varix at the outside, only slightly notched; on the inside a small denticle can be observed at the lower extremity of the sinus.

Canal: short, channeled but unnotched; inner lip smooth.

Measurements: 4.30 - 5.90 x 2.05 - 2.60 mm; average 5.00 x 2.40 mm.

Holotype: 5.45 x 2.55 mm.

Paratypes: 5 from the same lot." (van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978: 104).

Cythara thapsiae has been described over 25 years ago (Oberling, 1970) and it would be desirable to have the prevalence reverted by virtue of Art. 23.9 (ICZN, 1999). Regrettably, Oberling himself (1971) used the name *Cythara thapsiae* as the valid name of a species, making thus impossible the meeting of the first of two conditions for a name to be defined nomen oblitum (ICZN, 1999: Art. 23.9.1.1, "the senior synonym ... has not been used as a valid name").

The type material of *Cythara thapsiae* Oberling is lost (E. Neubert, pers. comm.). We have examined the unsorted residuals of the same sample of bioclastic sediment from Magnisi (Sicily) studied by J. J. Oberling and which yielded the lost type material of *Cythara thapsiae*. We have found in this sample a total of six species of *Mangelia*: 3 shells of *M. vauquelini* (Payraudeau, 1826), 6 shells of *M. stosiciana* Brusina, 1869, 3 shells of *M. paciniana* (Calcara, 1839), 1 shell of *M. unifasciata* (Deshayes, 1835), 12 shells of *M. taeniata* (Deshayes, 1835) and

12 shells that would unequivocally be classified as *M. fieldeni* (Figure 1A-G), and are the sole that fit quite well the description of *Cythara thapsiae*.

It is clear from this that the two names (*Cythara thapsiae* Oberling, 1970 and *Mangiliella fieldeni* van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978) refer to the same species, with Oberling's name prevailing for Priority.

Abbreviations used,

BA: Bruno Amati collection, Rome.
 DS: Danilo Scuderi collection, Belpasso, Catania (Italy).
 MCZR: Museo Civico di Zoologia, Rome (Italy).
 MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris (France).
 NMBE: Naturhistorisches Museum der Burgergemeinde Bern (Switzerland).
 MO: Marco Oliverio collection, Rome (Italy).
 MZUP: Museum of Zoology, University of Palermo (Italy).

SYSTEMATICS

Superorder CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960

Superfamily CONOIDEA Fleming, 1822

Family MANGELIIDAE P. Fischer, 1883

Genus *Mangelia* Risso, 1826

Type species: *Mangelia striolata* Risso, 1826: 221, pl. 8, fig. 101 (by subsequent designation Gray, 1847: 134)

Mangelia thapsiae (Oberling, 1970) comb. nov. (Figure 1A-J, Table I)

Cythara thapsiae Oberling, 1970: 4. - Oberling, 1971: 6

Mangiliella fieldeni van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978: 104

Cythara thapsiae Oberling, 1970: Tucker, 2004: 997

Type material: *Cythara thapsiae* Oberling. Neotype (NMBE 549732), here designated H 4.7 mm, W 2.2 mm, Magnisi (Sicily) beached bioclastic sediment (J.J. Oberling leg. 13.iii.1970). *Mangiliella fieldeni* van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1978. Holotype and 5 paratypes (BMNH 1911-10-26 - 8043-8049), Malta.

Other material examined: Italy. Magnisi, Sicily, beached bioclastic sediment (J.J. Oberling leg. 13.iii.1970), 11 sh (BA); Ognina, Sicily, beached, 10.x.1982, 1 sh (BA); Vendicari, Sicily, beached, 1994, 1 sh (BA); Scauri, Pantelleria Is., Sicily, -15/20 m, 2.vii.2006, 1 sh (BA), -13 m, 12.vi.1991, 1 sh (BA); Capo Asparano, Sicily, ix.1985, beached, 1 sh (BA); Cannizzaro, Sicily, -30/40 m, 2 sh (BA); Isola delle Correnti, Sicily, -15 m, 3 sh (MO); Scilla, Calabria, -43/44 m, vii.2015, 1 sh (BA). Malta. 8 sh (coll. Monterosato, MCZR, M15.16849); Bahar it-Caghaq, 2010, 1 sh (BA). Tunisia. Kerkennah Islands, vii.2015, 4 sh (BA).

Figure 1. A-J. *Mangelia thapsiae* (Oberling, 1970). A-F: neotype, Magnisi, Sicily (Italy), height 4.7 mm (NHMB). D: detail of the protoconch; E, F: detail of the teleoconch sculpture, penultimate (E) and last (F) whorls. G: Magnisi, Sicily (Italy), height 5.1 mm (BA). H: Cannizzaro, Sicily (Italy), height 4.3 mm (BA). I, J: Malta, height 4.6 mm and original label (MCZR).

Figura 1. A-J. *Mangelia thapsiae* (Oberling, 1970). A-F: neotipo, Magnisi, Sicilia (Italia), altura 4.7 mm (NHMB). D: detalle de la protoconcha; E, F: detalle de la escultura de la teleoconcha, penúltima (E) y última (F) vuelta. G: Magnisi, Sicilia (Italia), altura 5,1 mm (BA). H: Cannizzaro, Sicilia (Italia), altura 4,3 mm (BA). I, J: Malta, altura 4,6 mm y etiqueta original (MCZR).

Description of the neotype: (Figure 1A-F). Shell (Figure 1A-F) of medium size for the genus, height 4.7 mm, width 2.2 mm, aperture height 2.4 mm, height/width ratio 2.136, fusiform, not robust.

Protoconch paucispiral (Figure 1D), slender, of 1.3 convex whorls with deep

suture, maximum diameter 525 μ m, seemingly smooth, with only sinuose axial striae, before the protoconch/teleoconch boundary.

Teleoconch of 3.75 convex whorls, with angulate shoulder (shoulder inclination c. 55° on the first two whorls, c. 45° on the last whorls). Suture not very

Table I. Measurements of teleoconch and protoconch of topotypic specimens of *Mangelia thapsiae* (Oberling, 1970), in mm. Number 1 is the neotype.Tabla I. Medidas de la teleoconcha y protoconcha de especímenes topotípicos de *Mangelia thapsiae* (Oberling, 1970), en mm. El número 1 es el neotipo.

Teleoconch	1	2	3	4	5	Min-max	Mean
Height	4.7	5	5.1	4.6	4.7	4.6-5.1	4.82
Width	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.2	2.3	2.2-2.4	2.28
Aperture height	2.4	2.6	2.6	2.3	2.4	2.3-2.6	2.46
Height/Width ratio	2.136	2.173	2.125	2.090	2.043	2.043-2.173	2.113
N° of whorls	3.75	4	3.9	3.7	3.5	3.5-4	3.77
Spirals above aperture	13	10	9	8	8	8-13	9.6
Spirals last whorls	30	30	29	24	26	24-30	27.8
Axials last whorls	10	9	8	9	9	8-10	9
Protoconch							
N° of whorls	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3
Maximum diameter	0.525	0.450	0.500	0.500	0.533	0.450-0.533	0.501

deep, undulated (Figure 1E). Spiral sculpture (Figure 1F) of 30 unequal flat spiral cordlets on the last whorl, of which 13 above the aperture; cordlets very weak on the shoulder; 7-8 cordlets on the base stronger. Axial sculpture of 11 ribs on the last whorl (including the labial varix), angled, orthocline and slightly flexuose, as broad as the inters-

paces; fine and flexuose growth lines visible in the interspaces. Siphonal canal broad; posterior sinus shallow; labial varix slightly stronger than the axials, devoid of spirals, sharp.

Background colour light brown-orange, with a subsutural darker band, fading on the last half whorl.

Soft parts unknown.

REMARKS

Variation - (Figure 1G-I see also Table I) The number of spirals on the last whorl ranges from 15 to 30, of which 4-13 above the aperture, usually the more numerous the finer the spirals (and sometimes the broader the interspaces). Axials range 9-14. The range of shell size is 3.6-5.9 mm. Colour can be white, ivory or brownish, with a narrow or broad darker subsutural spiral band that may fade out on the last whorl and reappear on the apertural varix; specimens have a dark to light brownish background, and c. 10 lighter spiral bands on the body whorl are known. Some specimens have a darker protoconch.

We have examined also 8 shells in the Monterosato collection 'ex Fielden, fide Ponsonby' from Malta (MCZR),

conforming to the material at BMNH used by VAN AARTSEN & FEHR-DE WAL (1978: 104) for the description of *M. fieldeni*. They are all whitish, with a fine subsutural brownish spiral band and a brownish blotch on the outer lip; 15-25 spirals on the last whorls, of which 4-6 above the aperture, very weak on the subsutural ramp; 8 stronger cordlets on the base; height 3.6-5.0 mm.

M. vauquelini (Payraudeau, 1826) (Figure 2G) differs from *M. thapsiae* in its multispiral protoconch, very weak and finer spiral sculpture and larger size. *M. stosiciana* Brusina, 1869 (Figure 2I), in its multispiral protoconch and stronger spiral sculpture reaching the outer lip. *M. paciniana* (Calcara, 1839) (Figure 2A; syntype 2B-C), in its multispiral protoconch, rounded teleoconch shoulder,

different colour pattern with yellowish background, 5-6 fine darker spiral lines and darker subsutural band. *M. sicula* Reeve, 1846 (Figure 2J), in its marked shoulder only on the first three whorls, different sculpture, narrower base, monochrome coloration and larger size. *M. unifasciata* (Deshayes, 1835) (Figure 2D) in its multispiral protoconch, teleoconch whorls not shouldered, and different sculpture with alternating finer and more robust spiral cordlets. *M. taeniata* (Deshayes, 1835) (Figure 2H), in its almost lack of spiral sculpture (only a weak basal sculpture), narrower base and peculiar trichromic pattern.

Mangelia angelinae (Cecalupo & Quadri, 1996) (Figure 2E-F), originally described from northern Cyprus, has been considered as a synonym of *M. fieldeni* by BUZZURRO & GREPPI (1997). However, some constant features (e.g. squatter protoconch with axial sigmoid riblets on the final 0.3 whorls, teleoconch with stronger and less numerous axials and spirals), are diagnostic at the

species level (G. Spada & B. Sabelli, pers. comm.). The binomen "*Mangelia fieldeni* Montrs." has been listed by SCALIA (1900: 25) and MONCHARMONT ZEI (1961: 175) but in both case as *nomen nudum* and thus not available.

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Eike Neubert and the late Margret Gosteli (NMBE, Bern) provided informations on the type material of Oberling, and supplied the bioclastic sediment samples. Maurizio Sarà and Enrico Bellia (MZUP, Palermo), assisted during the study of the type material of Calcara. Danilo Scuderi (Belpasso, Catania) made samples from his collection available for study. Philippe Bouchet (MNHN, Paris), Serge Gofas (University of Malaga), Gianni Spada (Vaugrigneuse) and Bruno Sabelli (University of Bologna) provided very useful comments on mangeliid systematics and nomenclature.

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(Right page) Figure 2. A-J. *Mangelia* spp. A-C: *Mangelia paciniana* (Calcara, 1839), A: Nettuno (Italy) beached, height 5.6 mm (BA), B, C: syntype, Palermo, Sicily (Italy) and original label (MZUP). D: *Mangelia unifasciata* (Deshayes, 1835) Umag (Croatia), beached, height 5.3 mm (BA). E, F: *Mangelia angelinae* (Cecalupo & Quadri, 1996), Cyprus, height 3.7 mm and detail of the protoconch (MO). G: *Mangelia vauquelini* (Payraudeau, 1826), Portoroz (Slovenia), beached, height 6.5 mm (BA). H: *Mangelia taeniata* (Deshayes, 1835), Salina Is. (Italy) -35 m, height 3.8 mm (BA). I: *Mangelia stosiciana* Brusina, 1869, Giglio Is. (Italy) -38 m, height 4.7 mm (BA). J: *Mangelia sicula* Reeve, 1846, Palermo (Italy), height 11.8 mm (MCZR).

(Página derecha) Figura 2. A-J. *Mangelia* spp. A-C: *Mangelia paciniana* (Calcara, 1839), A: Nettuno (Italia), explayado, altura 5,6 mm (BA), B, C: sintipo, Palermo, Sicilia (Italia) y etiqueta original (MZUP). D: *Mangelia unifasciata* (Deshayes, 1835) Umag (Croacia), explayado, altura 5,3 mm (BA). E, F: *Mangelia angelinae* (Cecalupo y Quadri, 1996), Chipre, altura 3,7 mm y detalle de la protoconcha (MO). G: *Mangelia vauquelini* (Payraudeau, 1826), Portoroz (Eslovenia), explayado, altura 6,5 mm (BA). H: *Mangelia taeniata* (Deshayes, 1835), Salina Is. (Italia) -35 m, altura 3,8 mm (BA). I: *Mangelia stosiciana* Brusina, 1869, Giglio Is. (Italia) -38 m, altura 4,7 mm (BA). J: *Mangelia sicula* Reeve, 1846, Palermo (Italia), altura 11,8 mm (MCZR).

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